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Microstrip Patch Antennas For Uwb Applications Other Than Open Air Data Communications: A Review

Pillalamarri Laxman, A. Jain · Published 2019 · Computer Science

Micro strip patch antennas were already replaced several old generation antennas like wire antennas, half wave dipoles of hand held devices and various other portable long and short distance applications in all areas. The main advantage is their portability, low profile, cost of fabrication and several other parameters better than remaining designs. Most of the research is done on earth surface operated data communication antennas. This paper shows a clear picture of various methods that improved existing old methods of (unlike data communication in open air)patch micro strip antennas that used for UWB applications. The performance of the antenna related with its basic parameters. [LESS](#)

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